

Ultraviolet Absorption Spectrum of 2-Fluorobenzotrifluoride

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The near ultraviolet absorption spectrum of 2-fluorobenzotrifluoride vapour has been photographed on a Hilger Q-24 medium quartz spectrograph. The spectrum lying in the region 2764–2500 Å has been interpreted in terms of the excited state frequencies 108, 242, 403, 530, 889 and 1031 cm^{-1} and ground state frequencies 126 and 286 cm^{-1}

The ultraviolet absorption spectrum of benzotrifluoride has been investigated by Spomer¹ and the isomeric chlorobenzotrifluorides have been studied by Rao *et al.*². It has been observed that benzotrifluoride when substituted gave rise to diffuseness in the spectrum and the analysis of bands in the lower wavelength region becomes very difficult. The present communication reports the absorption spectrum of *o*-fluorobenzotrifluoride vapour. The vibrational bands have been interpreted with the help of the ground state frequencies observed in the infrared spectrum (authors' unpublished data). The assignments given for benzotrifluoride¹, isomeric chlorobenzotrifluorides² and *m*-aminobenzotrifluoride³ have been much useful in the analysis.

EXPERIMENTAL

The spectrum was photographed on a Hilger Q-24 Medium Quartz Spectrograph having a dispersion of nearly 13 Å/mm in the region under investigation. A cell of 20 cm length was used as the absorption column with a bulb attached to the middle of the cell as the reservoir for the chemical. The optimum condition for the best development of bands was found at 25° of the bulb containing the liquid. The chemical was obtained from Koch-Light Laboratories and was used without further purification. Copper arc spectrum was used as the comparison spectrum and the observed bands were measured on a Hilger L-76 comparator. The accuracy of measurement is estimated to be 5 cm^{-1} for sharp bands and 10 cm^{-1} for weak and diffuse bands. The spectrum is shown in Fig. 1.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

About fortyfive bands were observed in the region 2764–2500 Å. Table 1 gives the wave numbers, relative intensities and assignments of the bands. The (0, 0) band has been identified as the strong band at 36493 cm^{-1} (2739.4Å). This gives a shift of 1326 cm^{-1} towards red in comparison to the (0, 0) band of benzotrifluoride (Vide Table 2). The electronic transition is an allowed A'–A', the transition moment lying in the plane of the molecule. The 0–1 $\times \nu_4$ transitions observed are 126, 286 and 329 cm^{-1} . These could not be

1. H. Spomer and D. S. Lowe, *J. Op. Soc. Am.*, 1949, **39**, 840.
2. A. Rao and V. R. Rao, *J. Mol. Spectroscopy*, 1960, **4**, 43.
3. R. Amminamma, G. D. Baruah and K. P. R. Nair, *Indian J. Pure and Appl. Phys.*, 1969, **7**, 831.

Fig. 1. Ultraviolet Absorption spectrum of 2-fluorobenzotrifluoride.

TABLE I

Ultraviolet Absorption Spectrum of 2-Fluorobenzotrifluoride

Wavenumber cm^{-1}	Relative Intensity	$\Delta\nu$ cm^{-1}	Assignment
36164	vw	329	0-286-44
36207	w	286	0-286
36241	w	252	
36323	w	170	0-126-44
36367	w	126	0-126
36406	ms	87	0-2x44
36449	vs	44	0-44 (286-242)
36493	vvs	0	0-0
36601	w	108	0+108 (242-216)
36691	w	198	0+242-44
36735	s	242	0+242
36816	w	323	
36848	w	355	0+403-44
36896	s	403	0+403
37004	w	511	0+403+108
37023	m	530	0+530
37097	w	604	0+403+242-44
37138	w	648	0+403+242
37253	w	760	0+760
37299	m	806	0+2x403
37382	vs	889	0+889
37524	vs	1031	0+1031
37785	m	1292	0+889+403
38023	w	1530	0+889+403+242
38268	ms	1775	0+2x889
38510	ms	2017	0+2x889+242
38671	w	2178	0+2x889+403

s = strong, vs = very strong, w = weak, m = medium, vw = very weak.

correlated with any ground state frequencies (infrared and Raman) due to lack of data. The fundamental frequencies in the excited state i.e., the $0+1 \times \nu'_i$ transitions are 242, 403, 530, 760, 889 and 1031 cm^{-1} . The strong band at 530 cm^{-1} may be correlated with the frequency 538 cm^{-1} (assigned as the β'_1 component of $608 \text{ cm}^{-1} e_g^+$ of benzene) in the spectrum of benzotrifluoride¹. Similarly the weak band at 760 cm^{-1} may be attributed as due to C-CF₃ valence vibration in agreement with similar observation by Sponer and Lowe¹. The strong band at 889 cm^{-1} may be assigned to the totally symmetric carbon ring vibration in the excited state. In benzotrifluoride this mode appears at 926 cm^{-1} . The strong band at a separation of 44 cm^{-1} from the (0, 0) band is explained as a difference band ($-44 = -286 + 242$). Similarly the weak band at 100 cm^{-1} in the excited state has been explained as a difference band ($100 = 242 - 126$).

TABLE 2

The (0,0) bands and their shifts with respect to benzene

Molecule	(0,0) band (cm^{-1})	cm^{-1}
Benzene	38080	
Monofluorobenzene	37819	-270
Benzotrifluoride	37819	-270
<i>o</i> -chlorobenzotrifluoride	36598	-1491
<i>m</i> -chlorobenzotrifluoride	36539	-1550
<i>p</i> -chlorobenzotrifluoride	37476	-613
<i>o</i> -fluorobenzotrifluoride	36493	-1596

From Table 2 it is apparent that the shift of the (0, 0) band (as compared to benzene) in benzotrifluoride and monofluorobenzene is the same i.e., 270 cm^{-1} a phenomenon which has not been properly interpreted. The present investigation on the ultraviolet absorption spectrum of 2-fluorobenzotrifluoride shows that the substitution of both CF₃ and F groups together in the benzene ring leads to a large shift of the (0, 0) band ($= 1596 \text{ cm}^{-1}$). It is apparent that the result does not follow the usual additivity rule of Herzfeld⁴. This is also true in case of *o*- and *m*-chlorobenzotrifluoride. A proper explanation of these large shifts needs a careful theoretical calculation with required parameters.

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